

Catalysing regeneration through territorial labs: Living Lab innovation in declining agrarian landscapes

Authors

Nicolás Delgado Alcega¹, Ginevra D'Agostino¹, Gabriele Pizzi¹

¹ Liminal Associazione di Promozione Sociale, C.F. 96492980584, Via del Seminario 113, 00186 Roma RM

Abstract

This presentation introduces the Territorial Lab methodology, a model for embedded Living Labs tailored to the challenges of land abandonment and demographic decline in rural Europe. Developed by the authors, the model adapts Living and Land-Based Lab concepts to fragile agrarian territories, using short-format “Challenges” to iteratively constitute long-term experimental spaces that reactivate land stewardship incentives through localized food value chains. Two pilot projects—*Transitioning a Landscape*¹ and *Shaping the Ground*—were carried out in Monti Prenestini (Lazio, Italy) to develop and test this approach. The first engaged local stakeholders, mapped abandonment dynamics, and designed a 3-hectare Territorial Lab prototype with actionable incentive frameworks. The second piloted the lab through a participatory toolkit for arboreal biodiversity mapping with local farmers. Together, they explored how embedded experimentation can catalyse systemic outcomes by activating and reweaving relationships among producers, processors, distributors, and consumers. The Territorial Lab is an evolving platform that aligns co-creation with strategic ecosystem-building. Its success lies not only in data or tools produced, but in enabling self-sustaining configurations of local actors. It offers an emerging model for embedding innovation where mandates are absent contributing directly to EU missions like A Soil Deal for Europe.

Key words

Living Lab, land abandonment, territorial regeneration, agroecology, co-creation, food value chains

Problem Statement

Land abandonment and demographic decline in Europe's rural regions undermine not only ecosystems but also the food economies and cultural infrastructures that sustain local life. In such contexts, conventional planning tools and top-down innovation strategies fall short. There is a need for embedded, iterative approaches that can reweave fragmented actor networks and catalyse new incentives for land stewardship, particularly where no clear development mandate exists.

Methods/Approach

The authors developed the Territorial Lab methodology to address this gap. It proposes a long-term innovation platform constituted through short-format Challenges—modular engagements that combine spatial diagnostics, co-design, and prototyping grounded in principles of action research. This model was iteratively built through deep, multi-scalar stakeholder engagement.

Transitioning a Landscape established the conceptual and spatial blueprint for a 3-hectare Territorial Lab in Monti Prenestini. It involved over 70 mapped and categorized stakeholders, including local producers, processors, conservationists, educators, and public officials. Through interviews, charrettes, and field analysis, it produced actionable tools: from incentive frameworks and ecological zoning to value-chain typologies.

*Shaping the Ground*² was the first testbed within this plan. It piloted a participatory toolkit for mapping arboreal biodiversity with three local farmers. It allowed us to experiment with stewardship practices and visibility strategies on the ground, validating elements of the Territorial Lab model in real conditions.

Results/Outcomes

These Challenges demonstrated that embedded co-creation can not only surface latent local capacities but also initiate systemic reconfiguration. By positioning food value chains as levers for both ecological stewardship and economic differentiation, the Territorial Lab catalyses the formation of new, self-sustaining actor relationships—between landowners, processors, distributors, and public institutions.

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These relationships, once activated through experimentation, begin to operate autonomously allowing territories to move beyond diagnosis or pilot interventions and into structurally viable, place-based ecosystems. This outcome-oriented approach enables regions to embed innovation without needing top-down mandates, directly supporting strategic ambitions like *A Soil Deal for Europe*.

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